

EXPERIENCE OF AYURVEDIC TREATMENT IN YAKRIT VIKAR: A PATHWAY OF HEALING CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Yakrit Vikar (liver disorders) is a significant concern in *Ayurvedic* medicine, encompassing conditions like fatty liver, cirrhosis, hepatitis, and alcohol-induced liver dysfunction, predominantly associated with *Pitta dosha* imbalance and manifesting as *Pandu*, *Kamala*, *Yakritvridhi*, and *Yakrit Vidradhi*. Classical *Ayurvedic* texts emphasize the interconnectedness of organ systems, offering a holistic diagnostic and therapeutic approach. This case study evaluates *Ayurvedic* management in a 33-year-old male who visited Jeena Sikho Lifecare Limited Clinic, Bathinda, Punjab, India, presenting with weakness, constipation, and a past history of piles. He was diagnosed with *Yakrit Vikar* and treated with *Ayurvedic* interventions, alongside dietary and lifestyle modifications. Post-treatment, the patient experienced significant symptomatic relief, with improvements in general health and bowel movements. Laboratory reports showed a reduction in total bilirubin from 1.25 mg/dL to 0.85 mg/dL and indirect bilirubin from 0.78 mg/dL to 0.47 mg/dL, indicating enhanced liver function. This case highlights the potential of *Ayurvedic* therapies to correct *doshic* imbalances, restore *Agni*, and support detoxification in *Yakrit Vikar*, though broader clinical trials are essential for standardization and wider acceptance within integrative healthcare models.

KEYWORDS: *Yakrit Vikar*, *Ayurveda*, *Panchakarma*, *Pitta Vridhi*, *Samprapti*.

INTRODUCTION

Yakrit Vikar, or liver disorders, is a significant area of focus in *Ayurveda*, encompassing various conditions such as fatty liver disease, cirrhosis, and alcohol-related liver disease. *Ayurvedic* treatments aim to restore balance within the body, particularly addressing the *Pitta dosha*, which is often implicated in liver dysfunction. *Ayurvedic* texts classify liver disorders based on symptoms rather than as distinct entities, emphasizing the interconnectedness of bodily systems.^[1] Conditions like *Pandu* and *Kamala* illustrate the spectrum of liver disorders, highlighting the need for accurate diagnosis to tailor effective treatments.^[2,3]

Previous studies on *Yakrit Vikara* in *Ayurveda* have explored both the conceptual framework and clinical management of liver disorders. Research has highlighted the *Ayurvedic* classification of liver diseases, such as *Yakritvridhi* (enlarged liver), *Yakrit Kshaya* (liver atrophy), and *Yakrit Vidradhi* (liver abscess), and their association with *dosha* imbalances, particularly *Pitta* and *Kapha*. Clinical studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of *Ayurvedic* treatments in managing conditions like hepatitis, fatty liver, and liver abscesses. For instance, a case report showed significant improvement in liver function following treatment with *Ayurvedic* therapies in a patient with Hepatitis B.^[4] Moreover, the review of Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD) within *Ayurvedic* principles

emphasized *Santarpanajanya Vyadhi* (diseases due to excessive nourishment) and the use of *Ayurvedic* treatments to manage liver health.^[5] These studies indicate that *Ayurvedic* interventions, such as detoxification therapies and *Ayurvedic* formulations, offer promising results for managing liver diseases, though further clinical research is needed for comprehensive validation. Treatment approaches in *Ayurveda* include dietary and *Ayurvedic* interventions,

where formulations have shown effectiveness in managing alcohol-related liver disease by improving liver function tests and alleviating symptoms.^[6] Additionally, *Virechana* (purgation) therapy, particularly with *Trivrutta Churna* for *Nitya Virechana*, has demonstrated the potential to normalize liver function tests in patients with liver disorders.^[7] The *Samprapti ghataka*^[8] of this case study is mentioned in **Table 1**.

Table 1: The Samprapti Ghataka.

Parameter	Condition
<i>Dosha</i>	<i>Ranjaka Pitta, Koshtagata Kapha</i>
<i>Dooshya</i>	<i>Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa</i>
<i>Agni</i>	<i>Ranjakagni-Pachakagni</i>
<i>Ama</i>	<i>Jatharagnimandya Janya Ama</i>
<i>Srotas</i>	<i>Raktava and Rasavaha Srotas</i>
<i>Srotodushti</i>	<i>Sanga, Vimargagamana</i>
<i>Udbhavasthana</i>	<i>Amashaya</i>
<i>Sanchara Sthana</i>	<i>Rasa and Raktavaha Srotas and its Moola</i>
<i>Adhishtana</i>	<i>Yakrit</i>
<i>Vyakta Sthana</i>	<i>Udara, Twacha, Netra.</i>
<i>Roga Marga</i>	<i>Bahya and Abhyantara</i>

Clinical case studies indicate significant improvements in symptoms and hematological parameters following *Ayurvedic* treatment for conditions like non-alcoholic fatty liver disease.^[9,10,11] The holistic approach of *Ayurveda* not only targets the liver but also enhances overall health by improving digestion and detoxification processes.^[12] While *Ayurvedic* treatments for *Yakrit Vikar* show promise, it is essential to acknowledge the need for rigorous clinical trials to further validate these approaches. Integrating modern medical practices with traditional methods could enhance treatment efficacy and improve patient outcomes. This study explores the impact of *Ayurvedic* interventions in a 33-year-old male with *Yakrit Vikar*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

I. Case Report

A 33-year-old male visited Jeena Sikho Lifecare Limited Clinic, Bathinda, Punjab, on December 28, 2024. His evaluation included a thorough medical history, physical examination, and diagnostics. His mother had a history of Diabetes mellitus II. He came with the condition like weakness and improper defecation. He had a history of piles. He was taking antacid on a daily basis for past 2 years. He was diagnosed with *Yakrit Vikar*. The *Ashtastana Pareeksha* with vitals during the visit on December 28, 2024 is mentioned in **Table 2**. Laboratory investigation results during the treatment period are shown in **Table 3**.

Table 2: The Ashtastana Pareeksha with Vitals during the initial examination on December 28, 2024.

Parameter	Findings
	28-12-2024
<i>Nadi</i>	<i>Vataj Pittaj</i>
<i>Mala</i>	<i>Badha</i>
<i>Mutra</i>	<i>Ishat peet varna</i>
<i>Jiwha</i>	<i>Malin</i>
<i>Shabda</i>	<i>Spashta</i>
<i>Spashta</i>	<i>Anushna sheeta</i>
<i>Drik</i>	<i>Avikrit</i>
<i>Akriti</i>	<i>Madhyam</i>

Table 3: Laboratory investigation results on during the treatment period.

Parameter	Findings		
	Date	30-12-2024	24-01-2025
Total Bilirubin		1.25 md/dl	0.85 md/dl
Direct Bilirubin		0.47 mg/dl	0.38 mg/dl
Indirect Bilirubin		0.78 md/dl	0.47 md/dl

An accurately designed *Ayurveda* Diet was provided to the patient to complement the *Ayurvedic* treatments administered for *Yakrit Vikar*^[13]:

II. Treatment Plan

I. Diet Plan

Dietary Guidelines from Jeena Sikho Lifecare Limited Clinic

- Avoid wheat, refined foods, dairy, coffee, tea, and packaged foods.

- Do not eat after 8 PM.
- When eating solid foods, take small bites and chew each bite 32 times.

Hydration

- Sip 2 liters of hot water throughout the day and consume DAP tea twice daily. To prepare 750 ml of DAP tea, combine 2 cloves, 5 cardamom pods, 25 black pepper seeds, 2 cinnamon sticks, and a spoon of fennel seeds with hot water.
- Drink alkaline water (750 ml/day), made with ½ cucumber, ½ lemon, ginger, turmeric, tomato, 3 green chilies, coriander, mint leaves, and Tulsi.
- Drink black or green tea without milk or sugar.

Meal Timing and Structure

- Early Morning (5:45 AM): Chew 2 cloves, crushed garlic, and curry leaves.
- Breakfast (9:00 AM): Seasonal fruits like pomegranate, cucumber, tomato, or guava (Weight × 10 Kg).
- Morning Snacks (11:00 AM): *Mugda yusha*, red juice, and 4-5 soaked almonds.
- Lunch (12:30 PM - 2:00 PM): Plate 1: salad (Weight × 5 Kg) and Plate 2: millet recipes with proper hydration.
- Evening Snacks: Green juice (100-150 ml).
- Dinner (6:00 PM): Salad and fermented millets with chutney made from five leaves, onion, tomato, garlic, and green chili.

रूक्षः शीतोऽगुरुः स्वादुर्बहुवातशकृद्यवः।

स्थैर्यकृत् सकषायश्च [१] बल्यः श्लेष्मविकारनुत्॥१९॥

रूक्षः कषायानुरसो मधुरः कफपित्तहा।

मेदः क्रिमिविषघ्नश्च बल्यो वेणुयवो मतः॥२०॥^[14]

Fasting

- Fast once a week with coconut water.

Special Instructions:

- Sit in sunlight for 1 hour, morning and evening, with feet soaked in lukewarm water while chanting LUM, VUM, RUM, YUM, HUM, OM, and AUM in gyan mudra position.
- Offer thanks to the divine before eating or drinking.

II. Lifestyle Recommendations

1. Practice meditation for stress relief.
2. Perform Yoga (*Sukshma Pranayama* and *Sukhasana*) for 40 minutes daily.
3. Do oil pulling every day.
4. Ensure 6-8 hours of restful sleep each night.
5. Follow a structured daily routine for balance and organization.

Medicinal Interventions

The *Ayurvedic* treatment employed in this case included Dr. Shuddhi Powder, 32 Herbal Tea, LIV Shuddhi Tablet, Yakrit Shoth Har Vati, Arogya Vati tablet, Yakrit tonic, Amalpit Nashak, Mutral Vati and Dr. Nabhi oil. The medications prescribed for the patient during the treatment is outlined in **Table 4**. The details of the medicine prescribed are described in **Table 5**.

Table 4: The medications prescribed for the patient during the treatment.

Date	Medicines	Dosage with Anupana
28-12-2024	Dr. Shuddhi Powder	Half a teaspoon HS (<i>Nishikala</i> with <i>koshna jala</i>)
	Herbal tea	Early morning in empty stomach
	LIV Shuddhi	1 TAB BD (<i>Adhobhakta</i> with <i>koshna jala</i>)
	Yakrit Shoth Har Vati	1 TAB BD (<i>Adhobhakta</i> with <i>koshna jala</i>)
	Yakrit Tonic	20 ml BD (<i>Adhobhakta</i> with <i>sama matra koshna jala</i>)
	Arogya Vati tablet	1 TAB BD (<i>Adhobhakta</i> with <i>koshna jala</i>)
	Dr. Nabhi Oil	2 drops in Nabhi
25-01-2025	Yakrit Shoth Har Vati	1 TAB BD (<i>Adhobhakta</i> with <i>koshna jala</i>)
	Arogya Vati tablet	1 TAB BD (<i>Adhobhakta</i> with <i>koshna jala</i>)
	Amalpit Nashak	1 TAB BD (<i>Adhobhakta</i> with <i>koshna jala</i>)
	Mutral Vati	1 TAB BD (<i>Adhobhakta</i> with <i>koshna jala</i>)
	Yakrit Tonic	20 ml BD (<i>Adhobhakta</i> with <i>sama matra koshna jala</i>)

Table 5: The details of the medicine prescribed during the treatment.

Medicine	Ingredients	Therapeutic Effects
Dr. Shuddhi Powder	Trikatu, Triphala, Nagarmotha (<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>), Vayavidang (<i>Embelia ribes</i>), Chhoti Elaichi (<i>Elettaria cardamomum</i>), Tej Patta (<i>Cinnamomum tamala</i>), Laung (<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i>), Nisoth (<i>Operculina turpethum</i>), Sendha Namak, Dhaniya (<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>), Pipla Mool (<i>Piper longum</i> root), Jeera (<i>Cuminum cyminum</i>), Nagkesar (<i>Mesua ferrea</i>), Amarvati (<i>Achyranthes aspera</i>), Anardana (<i>Punica granatum</i>), Badi Elaichi (<i>Amomum subulatum</i>), Hing (<i>Ferula assafoetida</i>), Kachnar (<i>Bauhinia variegata</i>), Ajmod (<i>Trachyspermum ammi</i>), Sajjikshar, Pushkarmool (<i>Inula racemosa</i>), Mishri (<i>Saccharum officinarum</i>)	Vishahara, Deepan-pachan, Yakrit shodhana, Mutra vriddhi, Rasayana and Rakta shodhana
32 Herbal Tea	Gauzaban (<i>Echium amoenum</i>), Kulanjan (<i>Alpinia galanga</i>), Choti Elaichi (<i>Elettaria cardamomum</i>), Laung (<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i>), Badi Elaichi (<i>Amomum subulatum</i>), Badiyan Khtay (<i>Illicium verum</i>), Banafsha (<i>Viola odorata</i>), Jufa (<i>Clerodendrum serratum</i>), Ashwagandha (<i>Withania somnifera</i>), Mulethi (<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>), Punarnava (<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i>), Brahmi (<i>Bacopa monnieri</i>), Chitrak (<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>), Kali Mirch (<i>Piper nigrum</i>), Adoosa (<i>Adhatoda vasica</i>), Saunf (<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i>), Shankh Pushp (<i>Evolvulus alsinoides</i>), Tulsi (<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>), Arjuna (<i>Terminalia arjuna</i>), Motha (<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>), Senaye (<i>Cuscuta reflexa</i>), Sonth (<i>Zingiber officinale</i>), Majeeth (<i>Rubia cordifolia</i>), Sarfoka (<i>Sphaeranthus indicus</i>), Dalchini (<i>Cinnamomum verum</i>), Gulab (<i>Rosa spp.</i>), Green Tea (<i>Camellia sinensis</i>), Giloy (<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>), Tej Patta (<i>Cinnamomum tamala</i>), Lal Chandan (<i>Pterocarpus santalinus</i>), White Chandan (<i>Santalum album</i>), Pudina (<i>Mentha spicata</i>)	Deepan and pachan
LIV Shuddhi Tablet	Milk Thistle (<i>Silybum marianum</i>), Goduchi (<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>), Dandelion (<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>), Tulsi (<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>), Punarnava (<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i>), Amla (<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>) and Arjuna (<i>Terminalia arjuna</i>)	Yakrit shodhana, Pitta shamana, Rakta shodhana, Agni deepana and Mutra vriddhi
Yakrit Shoth Har Vati	Punarnava (<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i>), Kalimirch (<i>Piper nigrum</i>), Pippali (<i>Piper longum</i>), Vayavidanga (<i>Embelia ribes</i>), Devdaru (<i>Cedrus deodara</i>), Kutha Haldi (<i>Picrorhiza kurroa</i>), Chitrak (<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>), Harad (<i>Terminalia chebula</i>), Bahera (<i>Terminalia chebula</i> , <i>Terminalia bellirica</i>), Amla (<i>Embllica officinalis</i>), Danti (<i>Baliospermum montanum</i>), Chavya (<i>Piper chaba</i>), Indra Jon (<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>), Pipla Mool (<i>Piper longum</i>), Motha Kalajira (<i>Nigella sativa</i>), Kayphal (<i>Myrica esculenta</i>), Kutaki (<i>Picrorhiza kurroa</i>), Nisoth (<i>Operculina turpethum</i>), Saunth (<i>Zingiber officinale</i>), Kakd Singhi (<i>Cucumis sativus</i>), Ajwain (<i>Trachyspermum ammi</i>), Mandur Bhasma (<i>Ferrum</i>).	Yakrit shoth shamana, Rakta shodhana, Pitta shamana, Agni deepana and Vishahara
Arogya Vati tablet	Kajan (<i>Carthamus tinctorius</i>), Loh Bhasm (<i>Ferrum</i>), Abhrak Bhasm (<i>Mica</i>), Tamra Bhasm (<i>Copper</i>), Amalaki (<i>Embllica officinalis</i>), Vibhitak (<i>Terminalia bellirica</i>), Haritaki (<i>Terminalia chebula</i>), Chitrak (<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>), Katuka (<i>Picrorhiza kurroa</i>), Nimb Patra (<i>Azadirachta indica</i>)	Ojasvini, Rasayana, Agni deepana and shothohara
Yakrit tonic	Lal Punarnava (<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i>), Safed Punarnava (<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i>), Bala (<i>Sida cordifolia</i>), Atibala (<i>Abutilon indicum</i>), Patha (<i>Cyclea peltata</i>), Giloy (<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>), Chitrak (<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>), Kakoli (<i>Lilium polyphyllum</i>), Vasa (<i>Adhatoda vasica</i>), Nagarmotha (<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>), Ajwain (<i>Trachyspermum ammi</i>), Sonth (<i>Zingiber officinale</i>), Kali Mirch (<i>Piper nigrum</i>), Long (<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i>), Methi (<i>Trigonella foenum-graecum</i>), White Jeera (<i>Cuminum cyminum</i>), Roheda Chhal (<i>Stereospermum suaveolens</i>), Dalchini (<i>Cinnamomum verum</i>), Tejpatta (<i>Cinnamomum tamala</i>), Badi Elaichi (<i>Amomum subulatum</i>), Chhoti Elaichi (<i>Elettaria cardamomum</i>), Jaiphal (<i>Myristica fragrans</i>), Nagkesar (<i>Mesua ferrea</i>), Kankol (<i>Piper cubeba</i>), Mulethi (<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>), Laliki (<i>Terminalia chebula</i>), Mahua (<i>Madhuca longifolia</i>)	Yakrit shodhana, Pitta shamana, Rakta shodhana and Agni deepana
Amalpiti Nashak	Mulethi (<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>), Pudina (<i>Mentha spicata</i> or <i>Mentha arvensis</i>), Hing (<i>Ferula assa-foetida</i>), Chitrak (<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>), Jeera (<i>Cuminum cyminum</i>), Vidang (<i>Embelia ribes</i>), Ajwain (<i>Trachyspermum ammi</i>), Marich (<i>Piper nigrum</i>), Pipal (<i>Piper longum</i>), Shunthi (<i>Zingiber officinale</i>), Amla (<i>Embllica officinalis</i> / <i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>), Vibhitaki (<i>Terminalia bellirica</i>), Haritaki (<i>Terminalia chebula</i>), Shankh Bhasm (Calcined conch shell ash), Lavang (<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i>).	Pitta Shamana, Amla Pitta Nashak, Agni Deepana, Vata-Pitta Shamana and Rakta Shodhana
Mutral Vati	Kajjali , Loh bhasma , Vanga bhasma , Abhrak bhasma , Yavakshara (<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>), Gokshur (<i>Tribulus terrestris</i>), Haritaki (<i>Terminalia chebula</i>), Vibhitaki (<i>Terminalia bellirica</i>), Vasa (<i>Justicia adhatoda</i> , Synonym: <i>Adhatoda vasica</i>)	Pitta shamana, Agni deepana, Ajeerna nivarana and Ama pachana
Dr. Nabhi oil	Amla (<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>), Haritaki (<i>Terminalia chebula</i>), Bahera (<i>Terminalia bellerica</i>), Almond (<i>Prunus dulcis</i>), Jaiphal (<i>Myristica fragrans</i>), Ajwain (<i>Trachyspermum ammi</i>), Alsi (<i>Linum usitatissimum</i>), Long (<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i>), Camphor (<i>Cinnamomum camphora</i>), Olive (<i>Olea europaea</i>), Coconut (<i>Cocos nucifera</i>), Lemongrass (<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i>), Kali Jeeri (<i>Nigella sativa</i>), Ajmod (<i>Apium graveolens</i>), Guggul (<i>Commiphora wightii</i>), Giloy (<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>), Chirayata (<i>Swertia chirata</i>), Kalonji (<i>Nigella sativa</i>), Katu Taila (<i>Sesamum indicum</i>), Taramira (<i>Eruca sativa</i>), Til Tailam (<i>Sesamum indicum</i>).	Agni deepana, Ama pachana, Vata shamana and Rasayana

RESULT

Effectiveness of Ayurvedic Treatments: The patient underwent 2 months of Ayurvedic regimen, after the treatment he experienced noteworthy development in symptoms, which denotes the interventions used in the study are effective against *Yakrit Vikar*. After the treatment he was well oriented and got relief from symptoms like weakness and constipation which shows that the Ayurvedic interventions used in the case study are effective for this liver disorders. The conditions before and after treatment is mentioned in **Table 6**.

Table 6: The conditions before and after treatment.

Conditions	Before treatment	After treatment
Weakness	Severe weakness	mild weakness
Stool	Constipation	Relieved
Tongue	Coated	Coated
Urine	Pale yellow	Clear

Implications for Future Research

This study focused on a *Yakrit Vikar*, yielding promising results. However, due to the small sample size, further research with randomized controlled trials and larger cohorts is needed to confirm the safety, efficacy, and reliability of Ayurvedic treatments, helping to establish standardized therapeutic guidelines.

DISCUSSION

Ayurvedic treatment for *Yakrit Vikar* offers a viable substitute for conventional medical methods. This case study describes the application of several Ayurvedic treatments to a 33-year-old man who has been diagnosed with *Yakrit Vikar*. *Samprapti*^[15,16,17] of this case study is illustrated in **Fig 1**.

क्षाराम्ललवणात्युष्णविरुद्धासात्म्यभोजनात्
निष्पावमाषपिण्याकतिलतैलनिषेवणात्॥७॥
विदग्धेऽन्ने दिवास्वप्नाद्व्यायामान्मैथुनात्तथा
प्रतिकर्मर्तुवैषम्याद्वेगानां च विधारणात्॥८॥
कामचिन्ताभयक्रोधशोकोपहतचेतसः।
समुदीर्णं यदा पित्तं हृदये समवस्थितम्॥९॥
वायुना बलिना क्षिप्तं सम्प्राप्य धमनीर्दश।
प्रपन्नं केवलं देहं त्वङ्मांसान्तरमाश्रितम्॥१०॥
प्रदूष्य कफवातासृक्त्वङ्मांसानि करोति तत्।
पाण्डुहारिद्रहरितान् वर्णान् बहुविधांस्त्वचि॥११॥
स पाण्डुरोग इत्युक्तः ...।१२।^[18]

Fig.1: Samprapti of this case study.

During his two months of Ayurvedic treatment, he underwent Ayurvedic therapy regimen. *Yakrit Vikar* begins with *Nidana Sevana*, such as the intake of *Amla*, *Lavana*, *Ushna*, *Madya*, and incompatible food (*Viruddha Ahara*), which leads to *Dosha Prakopa*, predominantly of *Pitta*, along with possible involvement of *Vata* and *Kapha*. This triggers *Agni Mandya* (impairment of *Jatharagni* and *Dhatvagni*), resulting in the formation of *Ama* (metabolic toxins). *Ama* accumulates and obstructs the *Raktavaha* and *Annavaah Srotas*, causing *Srotorodha*, which in turn leads to *Rakta Dushti* (vitiation of blood). Prolonged *Rakta Dushti* results in *Yakrit Dushti*, impairing the structure and function of the liver, manifesting as conditions like *Kamala*, *Yakrit Shotha*, *Yakrit Vidradhi*, or *Pleeha-Yakrit Vriddhi*.

In this pathological sequence, Ayurvedic interventions play a crucial role. Dr. Shuddhi Powder and 32 Herbal Tea help in the early stage by correcting *Agni*, eliminating *Ama*, and pacifying the vitiated *Doshas* through *Amahara*, *Deepana-Pachana*, and *Śodhana* actions. LIV Shuddhi Tablet, Amalpit Nashak, and Arogya Vati primarily pacify *Pitta*, regulate *Vata* and *Kapha*, and support *Raktaprasadana*. As *Srotorodha* and inflammation progress, *Yakrit Shotha* Har Vati, *Yakrit Tonic*, and Dr. Nabhi Oil provide *Shothahara*, *Yakrtvishodhana*, and *Srotovishodhana* actions, which help detoxify the liver and restore *Rakta* flow. *Mutral Vati* supports *Mutravaha Srotovishodhana* and aids in removing accumulated toxins via the urinary system.

Together, these formulations address various stages of the pathogenesis and support the restoration of *Doshic* balance, enhancement of *Agni*, purification of *Rakta*, and rejuvenation of the *Yakrit*.

This case study highlights the potential benefits of *Ayurvedic* therapy for managing *Yakrit Vikar*. *Ayurvedic* treatment, offer a more accessible, cost-effective approach, addressing underlying imbalances that contribute to liver dysfunction. While promising, further research is needed to confirm the effectiveness, safety, and reliability of *Ayurvedic* treatments in *Yakrit Vikar* management.

CONCLUSION

This case study evaluating the treatment of *Yakrit Vikar* through *Ayurvedic* interventions yields the following findings:

Symptoms: Upon admission, the patient presented with general weakness and Constipation. After *Ayurvedic* treatment, significant improvements were observed. The patient reported relief from weakness and constipation, with no new symptoms emerging, suggesting a marked improvement in liver function and overall health.

Vitals and Investigations: There was a notable reduction in general weakness and constipation, reflecting positive changes in both lifestyle and diet. The total bilirubin reduced from 1.25 md/dl to 0.85 md/dl and Indirect bilirubin reduced from 0.78 md/dl to 0.47 md/dl.

In summary, holistic *Ayurvedic* therapies for *Yakrit Vikar* showed promising results, including improvements in laboratory test results, vital signs, and symptoms. The *Ayurvedic* treatment appears to enhance liver function, alleviate *Yakrit Vikar* symptoms, and improve overall health.

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